

Ear Recognition as Biometric

(Pengecaman Telinga sebagai Biometrik)

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ABSTRACT

Biometrics refers to detailed information about a person's body, such as color patterns in their eyes that can be used to prove who the individual is. Ear shape has played an important role in forensic science and its use by law enforcement agencies. The structure of the ear also does not change radically over time. This work on new ear biometrics focuses on developing automated techniques for ear recognition. The study of identification of the ear as a biometric began in 1986 until 2012. This study has used a database from IIT Kanpu and the University of Science and Technology Beijing (USTB). The database contains at least 500 ear images. For 26 years many methods have been implemented and most of them have achieved high success rates. In this study there are several problems that the complex ear structure can reduce the accuracy of the ear recognition system and different angles of the ear image can cause constraints to obtain the desired ear image orientation. The objective of the study is to process the ear image by following the correct procedure, segment the image to obtain the desired ear area and make an assessment based on the results of the ear recognition system obtained. In the ear recognition system there are several steps namely the ear image database which contains the ear image at different angles, pre-processing to improve the quality of the ear image and binary conversion. Next, the extraction of ear features to obtain canny edge ear images and the Peak Signal to Noise Ratio (PSNR) process to measure the quality of the ear images. The evaluation of the results of the ear recognition system involves the process of matching the characteristics of the ear image and the percentage of overlapping images to obtain the value of the recognition rate. In this study 30 samples of ear images (right) from different angles were used. The quality in all these images can be measured and there are differences in value due to different pixel image sizes. All ear images can be criticized for evaluation. The ear recognition system consists of several steps and each step must be followed correctly to get the desired result.

Keywords: Ear; biometrics; recognition;

ABSTRAK

Biometrik merujuk kepada maklumat terperinci tentang badan seseorang, seperti corak warna di mata mereka yang boleh digunakan untuk membuktikan siapa individu tersebut. Bentuk telinga telah memainkan peranan penting dalam sains forensik dan penggunaannya oleh agensi penguatkuasa undang-undang. Struktur telinga juga tidak berubah secara radikal dari masa ke masa. Kerja-kerja mengenai biometrik telinga baru ini memberi tumpuan kepada membangunkan teknik automatik untuk pengecaman telinga. Kajian pengecaman telinga sebagai biometrik telah bermula pada tahun 1986 sehingga 2012. Kajian ini telah menggunakan pangkalan data dari IIT Kanpu dan Universiti Sains dan Teknologi Beijing (USTB). Pangkalan data mengandungi sekurang-kurangnya 500 imej telinga. Selama 26 tahun banyak kaedah telah dilaksanakan dan kebanyakannya telah mendapat kadar kejayaan yang tinggi. Dalam kajian ini terdapat beberapa masalah iaitu struktur telinga yang kompleks boleh mengurangkan ketepatan sistem pengecaman telinga dan sudut imej telinga yang berlainan boleh menyebabkan kekangan untuk mendapatkan orientasi imej telinga yang diinginkan. Objektif dalam kajian adalah untuk memproses imej telinga dengan mengikut prosedur yang betul, membuat segmentasi imej telinga untuk mendapatkan kawasan telinga yang diinginkan dan membuat penilaian berdasarkan kepada keputusan sistem pengecaman telinga yang diperolehi. Dalam sistem pengecaman telinga terdapat beberapa langkah iaitu

pangkalan data imej telinga yang mengandungi imej telinga yang berlainan sudut, pra-pemprosesan untuk meningkatkan kualiti imej telinga dan penukaran binari. Seterusnya, pengekstrakan ciri telinga untuk mendapatkan imej telinga canny edge dan proses Peak Signal to Noise Ratio (PSNR) untuk mengukur kualiti imej telinga. Penilaian keputusan sistem pengecaman telinga melibatkan proses padanan ciri imej telinga dan peratusan gambar bertindih untuk mendapatkan nilai kadar pengecaman. Dalam kajian ini 30 sampel imej telinga (kanan) yang berlainan sudut telah digunakan. Kualiti dalam semua imej tersebut dapat diukur dan terdapat perbezaan dari segi nilai disebabkan oleh saiz imej piksel yang berlainan. Semua imej telinga dapat dikecam untuk penilaian. Sistem pengecaman telinga terdiri daripada beberapa langkah dan setiap langkah harus diikuti dengan betul untuk mendapatkan keputusan yang diingini.

Kata Kunci: telinga; biometrik; pengecaman;

INTRODUCTION

The study of ear recognition as a biometric began in 1986 until 2012. This study uses a database from IIT Kanpu and Beijing University of Science and Technology (USTB). The database contains at least 500 ear images. For 26 years, many methods have been implemented and most of them have achieved high success rates. According to researchers (Nadler & Smith 1993) there are some basic problems in this study that is to identify objects as belonging to a particular group. Moreover, pattern recognition assumes that objects associated with one group are closer to each other. Variation also affects the accuracy of system identification (Li & Jain 2009). To identify this problem, the process is divided into two basic tasks namely descriptive task of producing object attributes using feature extraction techniques and classification task of assigning group labels to objects based on those attributes to the classifier (Rettberg et al. 2007).

The ear recognition framework comprises of two sections which are ear segmentation and ear recognition. The initial segment which is ear segmentation contains three stages to be specific skin detection, morphological activity and ear extraction. The subsequent part is ear recognition including the qualities of extraction measures (little wave estimates and Key Component Analysis) and characterization of neural system arrangement. In the ear recognition segment, there are various calculations that can be utilized to extract features and one of them is to utilize wavelet changes to acquire surmised coefficients that will be standardized to coordinate in paired structure [0-1].

This standardized picture will be saved as a picture (.jpg), and this will be a gray value in the range [0-255]. Further examination of key parts, (Mayya and Saii 2016) will be utilized to acquire the last element vector of each picture. Key part investigation is a strategy for diminishing element vector measurements while keeping up variety in datasets. A low-dimensional space is called an eigenvial space characterized by a lot of vein vector datasets utilized in arrangement. In ear biometrics, eigenvalues and eigenvectors were determined for

gatherings of activity pictures, and ear space was chosen dependent on eigenvectors. In the wake of figuring the eigenvalues of every one of the moving toward pictures, the eigenvector comparing to the eigenvalues surpassing the limit ($0.5e + 008$) is chosen, while the others are killed. This procedure will create the last vector feature. Besides, this study proposes a methodology for identifying online ear images using geometric features. The ear identification system occurs based on ear height lines, reference lines and angles. This process involves installing the outer ear curve and finding the correct ear orientation. Canny edge detection is used to find the edge of the ear (Dhivya & Prakash 2016). Through this study, ear images based on full human recognition are introduced. Ear images are obtained through skin detection and morphological surgery.

Features extracted using the Key Component Analysis algorithm. The study was conducted on 370 ear images and the system achieved a 98.9% recognition rate. In ear segmentation, the framework figured out how to segment the ear picture accurately from 445 side-by-side pictures, fizzled in the other 15 pictures and arrived at a figure of 96.73%. In addition, in the study of 3D local surface features, which is the identification of errors in matching with local 3D features only. This study was conducted using 200 ear images from 100 different subjects and the recognition rate was 84% to 90%. In the study a good match with the Iterative Closest Point (ICP) algorithm was also used (McKay et. Al. 1992). This algorithm is considered one of the most accurate algorithms for the registration of two data points provided the data set is roughly adjusted. Some matching failures using local 3D features can only be restored with fine alignment with ICP after initial alignment using local 3D features. For ICP algorithms the recognition rate increases from 90% to 96%.

METHODOLOGY

Database

AMI Ear Database was created by Esther Gonzalez (2012) during her work in Computer Science PhD. The database consists of ear images collected from students, teachers and staff of the Department of Computer Science at the Universidad de Las Palmas de Gran Canaria (ULPGC), Las Palmas, Spain. Images were taken in a closed environment. The database was obtained from 100 different subjects in the age range of 19-65 years. For each individual, seven ear images (six right ear pictures and one left ear image) were taken. All photos were taken using a Nikon D100 camera, under the same lighting conditions, with the subject sitting at a distance of about two meters from the camera and seeing some early fixed signs.

Five images of the right ear are obtained by having the individual face forward and labeled as (FRONT), facing upwards and labeled as (UP). Individuals are also facing down and labeled as (DOWN) and facing left and right and labeled as (LEFT) and (RIGHT). The sixth image of the right ear was taken with the subject facing forward as well but with a different camera focal length and labeled as (ZOOM). The last image is the left ear labeled as (BACK) which is the subject facing forward and with the same camera focal length from the previous five images as shown in Figure 1. The database of 700 images has been numbered sequentially for each subject with integer identification numbers. The resolution of this image is 492×702 pixels and all these images are available in jpeg format. In this study, six pictures of the right ear will be used.

FIGURE 1 Sample Images from AMI Ear Database Which are republished in an Image Set

Pre-Processing

Ear image pre-processing is an early stage of image processing. The image database contains left and right ear images. In pre-processing the purpose of this process is to improve the visual appearance of the image. The original image of this ear is represented by a 3-dimensional matrix which are height with width with colorplane as shown in the Figure 2. The image in jpeg format will be converted to png format. The purpose of this process is to

ensure that there is no loss in image quality every time the image is opened and stored. Besides, when the image is converted to png format, the image resolution will change from 492×702 pixels to 517×735 pixels. Next, the colored image will be converted to a gray scale image. This gray scale image is represented by a 2-dimensional matrix of height and width as shown in Figure 3. The image resolution is 517×735 pixels.

FIGURE 2 Original Ear Image

FIGURE 3 Grayscale Ear Image

Binary Image Conversion

In the process, the gray scale image of the ear will be converted to a binary image. A binary image is an image consisting of pixels that can have one of two identical colors namely black and white as shown in Figure 4. This means that each pixel of the image is stored as one bit. This ear binary image is labeled as input image without noise. Each ear image has a different threshold value. The threshold value for the binary image in Figure 4 is 128. This process is done by measuring the area of the ear image area and removing the image pixels less than the value of 30. The binary image resolution is 517×735 pixels.

FIGURE 4 Binary Image

Ear Feature Extraction

In the process of extraction of the ear feature, the binary ear image will be converted to the edge detection image as shown in Figure 5. After that, canny edge detection will be used to extract the ear feature and get the desired ear area. There are several steps that must be taken to obtain the final ear image result. The first is to use threshold values. The threshold values used in this process are 0.075 (low) and 0.175 (high). The Gaussian filter coefficient, B is also used as in Equations (1) and (2).

$$B = [2, 4, 5, 4, 2; 4, 9, 12, 9, 4; 5, 12, 15, 12, 5; 4, 9, 12, 9, 4; 2, 4, 5, 4, 2] \quad (1)$$

$$B = 1/159 \times B \quad (2)$$

The next step is to find the convolution of the image using the Gaussian coefficient, A as shown in Equation (3).

$$A = \text{conv2}(img, B, 'same') \quad (3)$$

where:

A = Convolution Image

B = Coefficient Gaussian Filter

Next is to find the convolution of the image by using horizontal filter and vertical filter as shown in Equations (4) and (5).

$$\text{Filtered}_x = \text{conv2}(A, KG_x, 'same') \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Filtered}_y = \text{conv2}(A, KG_y, 'same') \quad (5)$$

where:

Filtered_x = Convolution image by using horizontal filter

Filtered_y = Convolution image by using vertical filter

KG_x = Horizontal Filter

KG_y = Vertical Filter

After finding the convolution of the image by using the horizontal filter and vertical filter, the direction / orientation will be calculated as in Equations (6) and (7).

$$\text{arah} = \text{atan2}(\text{Filtered}_y, \text{Filtered}_x) \quad (6)$$

$$\text{arah} = \text{arah} \times 180/\pi \quad (7)$$

Next an adjustment for the negative direction will be made to make all the positive directions and the direction closest to 0, 45, 90, or 135 degrees also adjusted. The magnitude of the ear image will be calculated as shown in Equations (8) and (9)

$$\text{magnitude} = \sqrt{(\text{Filtered}_x^2) + (\text{Filtered}_y^2)} \quad (8)$$

$$\text{magnitude2} = \sqrt{(\text{magnitude})} \quad (9)$$

After finding the magnitude, the binary input image can be searched using Equation (10).

$$BW = BW \times \text{magnitude2} \quad (10)$$

where:

BW = Binary Input Image

After finding the binary input image, non-maximum suppression will be performed on the ear image. The value of hysteresis thresholding will be calculated using Equations (10) and (11).

$$T_{Low} = T_{Low} \times \max(\max(BW)) \quad (11)$$

$$T_{High} = T_{High} \times \max(\max(BW)) \quad (12)$$

where:

T_{Low} = Low threshold value

T_{High} = High threshold value

In addition, 8-connected components in this process are used where the pixels are connected if the edges or corners are in contact. Two adjacent pixels are part of the same object if both are and are connected along a horizontal, vertical, or diagonal direction. By using these steps, the result of the final ear image can be obtained as in Figure 6. Canny edge image resolution is 543×769 pixels.

FIGURE 5 Edge Detection Ear Image

FIGURE 6 Canny Edge Ear Image

After obtaining the canny edge ear image, the PSNR process will be performed on the original ear image and the canny edge ear image. The purpose of this process is to measure the quality of the picture. This process is done by displaying the original image of the ear to maximize the image. After that, get the second picture by adding sound to the first picture. The Gaussian value used is 0.003. After obtaining the two pictures, the square error image can be obtained as in Figure 7 and calculated. To find the Mean Squared Error (MSE), the sum of square error images is divided by the number of elements. Peak Signal to Noise Ratio (PSNR) can be found using Equation (13).

$$PSNR = 10 \log_{10} (256^2 \div MSE) \quad (13)$$

This process is repeated using canny edge ear images. After finding the PSNR values for the two images, the values will be compared.

FIGURE 7 Squared Error Image

Feature Matching of Ear Image

The evaluation of the Ear Recognition System is done by matching the features of the ear image and calculating the percentage of overlapping image. Ear image feature matching is done by finding the appropriate point between the ear image pairs using local neighborhoods and the Harris algorithm. After matching the ear image feature, the percentage value of the image overlap will be calculated to get the recognition rate value. The process of matching the ear image feature is done by finding the appropriate point between the pair of ear images using local

neighborhoods and the Harris algorithm. The Harris algorithm is an algorithm used to extract angles and infer images features. This process involves two different images of the same individual. The images used are the original image of the ear and canny edge ear image as shown in Figure 8.

FIGURE 8 Original Ear Images (RIGHT) and Canny Edge Ear Images (FRONT)

The first step in this process is to find the angles of both pictures. After finding the angles of both images, this algorithm will extract the neighborhood features of the image. Later those features will be matched. After matching the features, the algorithm will take the location of the appropriate point for each image. Finally illustrate the appropriate points to see the translation effect between the two pictures although there is some confusion as in Figure 9.

FIGURE 9 Ear Image Features Matching Percentage of Image Overlapped

After performing the process of matching both ear images, the percentage of overlapping images will be calculated. This process is done by removing non-overlapping photo areas and there are several steps to calculate overlapping images. The first step is to find the number of components connected in the picture. Next is to determine the largest component in the picture and delete it (set all pixels to 0). With this, non-overlapping photos will be removed. Based on the overlapping pictures, the total number of points and the number of the number of points matched can be obtained. Based on the number matched points, the recognition rate can be obtained.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this research, a total of 30 samples of right ear images were used. Each individual has 6 samples of ear images with different angles. 6 ear images consist of ear image (BACK), ear image (FRONT), ear image (UP), ear image (BELOW), ear image (RIGHT) and ear image (ZUM)

Peak Signal to Noise Ratio (PSNR) Results

The main purpose of this process is to measure the quality of the picture. This process is done to two ear images namely the original image of the ear and the ear image of the canny edge. This process was performed for 30 ear image samples. Each individual has 6 samples of ear images and this process is done to 5 individuals. PSNR results for each individual are made in tabular form to see the differences as in Tables 1 and 2. There is little difference in PSNR value between the original image and the canny edge image due to the different pixel image sizes.

Table 1 PSNR RESULTS (ORIGINAL EAR IMAGE)

	INDIVIDUAL 1 (dB)	INDIVIDUAL 2 (dB)	INDIVIDUAL 3 (dB)	INDIVIDUAL 4 (dB)	INDIVIDUAL 5 (dB)
EAR IMAGE (BACK)	25.26	25.27	25.45	25.45	25.48
EAR IMAGE (FRONT)	25.25	25.48	25.45	25.54	25.49
EAR IMAGE (RIGHT)	25.31	25.74	25.85	25.65	25.63
EAR IMAGE (UP)	25.29	25.48	25.49	25.55	25.42
EAR IMAGE (DOWN)	25.26	25.49	25.50	25.53	25.47
EAR IMAGE (ZOOM)	25.26	25.45	25.53	25.51	25.45

Table 2 PSNR RESULTS (CANNY EDGE EAR IMAGE)

	INDIVIDUAL 1 (dB)	INDIVIDUAL 2 (dB)	INDIVIDUAL 3 (dB)	INDIVIDUAL 4 (dB)	INDIVIDUAL 5 (dB)
EAR IMAGE (BACK)	28.27	28.25	28.26	28.27	28.25
EAR IMAGE (FRONT)	28.25	28.27	28.26	28.26	28.26
EAR IMAGE (RIGHT)	28.28	28.26	28.25	28.27	28.25
EAR IMAGE (UP)	28.26	28.26	28.26	28.26	28.25
EAR IMAGE (DOWN)	28.26	28.26	28.24	28.25	28.25
EAR IMAGE (ZOOM)	28.26	28.27	28.24	28.27	28.26

Ear Recognition Results

The ear recognition process is done by matching the original image of the ear and the image of the ear canny edge. The two images are different but from the same individual as shown in Table 3. For matching ear images, the recognition rate can be calculated. Each

individual has a different rate of identification and image matching. Ear recognition results are made for each individual in tabular form to see the difference in the recognition value.

Table 3 Ear Recognition Results

MATCHED EAR IMAGES	INDIVIDUAL 1 (%)	INDIVIDUAL 2 (%)	INDIVIDUAL 3 (%)	INDIVIDUAL 4 (%)	INDIVIDUAL 5 (%)
ORIGINAL EAR IMAGE (RIGHT) AND CANNY EDGE EAR IMAGE (FRONT)	89.66	90.46	85.16	70.23	84.61
ORIGINAL EAR IMAGE (FRONT) AND CANNY EDGE EAR IMAGE (RIGHT)	70.83	88.46	86.29	90.46	92.86
ORIGINAL EAR IMAGE (UP) AND CANNY EDGE EAR IMAGE (RIGHT)	87.46	81.64	73.16	85.38	83.69
ORIGINAL EAR IMAGE (RIGHT) AND CANNY EDGE EAR IMAGE (UP)	80.21	86.12	76.26	95.62	83.62
ORIGINAL EAR IMAGE (DOWN) AND CANNY EDGE EAR IMAGE (FRONT)	81.63	82.65	90.38	70.85	85.38
ORIGINAL EAR IMAGE (FRONT) AND CANNY EDGE EAR IMAGE (DOWN)	82.67	83.61	84.62	91.83	75.22
ORIGINAL EAR IMAGE (ZOOM) AND CANNY EDGE EAR IMAGE (RIGHT)	85.61	79.68	82.16	88.38	92.86
ORIGINAL EAR IMAGE (RIGHT) AND CANNY EDGE EAR IMAGE (ZOOM)	81.49	90.47	81.64	82.96	73.16

30 ear image samples were used in this study and ear image processing was performed on all ear images. The Peak Signal to Noise Ratio (PSNR) process is also done to measure the quality of the picture. For the ear recognition process, all ear images can be matched except for the original ear image (BACK) and canny edge ear image (BACK) due to the same angle as the left ear image

CONCLUSION

The main objective in this project is to process the

ear image by following the correct procedure. In this project, there are 30 samples of ear images and all the ear images have been processed according to the correct procedure even though the structure and angle of the ear images are different. The procedure for processing ear images consists of several steps such as pre-processing, conversion of color images to gray scale images, conversion to binary images and conversion to canny edge images. The second objective is to segment the image of the ear using the correct technique to obtain the desired ear area. To get the desired image area of the ear, the ear image

will be converted to a binary image. In binary images there are two colors namely black and white. In this project, the area of the desired ear image is white, and the area of the unwanted ear image is black. With this, the process of segmenting the ear image can be done easily. The third objective is to do an evaluation based on the results of the ear recognition system obtained. After processing the ear image, a matching of the ear image will be performed. This process involves two images which are the original image of the ear and the canny edge ear image. The two images are different but from the same individual. After matching the two images, the recognition rate can be searched by calculating the percentage of overlapping images.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I would like to thank my supervisor, Assoc. Prof. Ir. Dr. Nasharuddin Zainal for his guidance through this research.

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